

Digital Twin for DCs: A Reference Architecture Based on BIM, IoT and Analytics Control

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Abstract— Data centers (DCs) represent one of the most energy-intensive and operationally critical categories of buildings, supporting essential digital services such as cloud computing, large-scale data storage, and artificial intelligence applications. Their operation is characterized by complex interdependencies between information technology loads, cooling infrastructures, power distribution systems, and environmental conditions. Ensuring efficiency, reliability, and resilience under these constraints remains a significant challenge for operators and designers alike. In recent years, the concept of Digital Twin (DT) has emerged as a promising paradigm to address this complexity by enabling a continuously updated digital representation of physical systems, enriched with real-time data and analytical capabilities.

Despite increasing attention in both academia and industry, DT solutions for buildings and DCs remain largely fragmented. Existing approaches often focus on individual aspects such as visualization, simulation, or monitoring dashboards, while failing to provide robust integration between design data, operational measurements, and control systems. A recurring limitation concerns the lack of interoperability between Building Information Modeling (BIM) data and Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructures, which prevents the construction of coherent and scalable DT systems.

This paper proposes a reference architecture for DT applied to DCs, grounded in the integration of BIM-based representations, real-time IoT data acquisition, analytical models, and control mechanisms. The architecture adopts a layered perspective, separating concerns related to data management, semantic integration, modeling, analytics, and actuation, while maintaining consistency across these layers. Informed by recent reviews on building-scale DT, the proposed approach addresses the well-known bottlenecks associated with BIM usage and data acquisition. The contribution of this work lies in providing an architectural blueprint able to support interoperability and reuse, offering a structured foundation for the development of advanced DT solutions in DC environments, and complemented by practical metrics that make DT implementations assessable beyond project-specific prototypes.

Keywords — *Digital Twin, DCs, BIM, IFC, IoT, Reference Architecture, Smart Buildings; HPC*

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, DCs are increasing infrastructure due to the significant rise in the adoption of AI and Machine Learning (ML), and the consequent high performance computational requirements of workloads execution [1, 10]. Indeed, HPC DCs are the backbone of modern research and industry, enabling advancements in AI, scientific simulations, and big data analytics.

According to the literature, a DC can be defined as a physical space where computers, servers, IT components and storage devices work together in a network system [2]. With the increasing computational demand, it's expected to evolve over time, improving in infrastructure, dimensions, equipment and technologies [3, 11]. Due to the complexity of this system, DC operators and designers have to face several challenges, mainly dealing with temperature control, power usage and energy demands management, and physical space design [2].

Furthermore, focusing on the DCs needs and the recent overall government restrictions for the energy use, cooling system and energy management become key topics in the DC domains [4, 11]. Indeed, energy-consumption is one of the most significant issues and its high demand is expected to increase through time [4]. Consuming elements in DC can be identified in the system components, in the cooling system and in the power distribution network [5], amounting to 90% of the DC energy consumption [6]. A critical parameter lies in the Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) ratio which considers the overhead power, relating to the energy consumption of the IT equipment with the one entering the DC. [4,6,7]. In DCs, PUE values should state near the value of 1 but it usually has a value of 2, or 1.2 in the state of the art [4].

The operation of HPC DCs accounts for a substantial share of global electricity use and greenhouse gas emissions. Amid growing concerns about climate change and environmental degradation, the demand for more energy-efficient and sustainable HPC systems has never been more urgent. The DCs energy consumption leads them to be great CO₂ emission producers, so new advances in technology exploitation to reduce CO₂ emissions, energy cost and consumption should be pursued [6].

The challenge lies in balancing the need for high computational power with environmental responsibility. Current HPC facilities largely rely on fossil fuels, and very few integrate renewable energy sources, such as solar or hydrogen-based systems, or adopt innovative approaches like waste heat reuse to mitigate their environmental footprint. Moreover, advancement in Renewable Energy Sources (RES), enhances the environmental perspective, leading to the concept of Green DC (GDC), which integrates conventional power supply with RES solutions [8]. RES such as photovoltaic (PV) and hydrogen-based fuel cell systems (FCS), promise to improve the DC sustainability, thanks to the low costs and the clean energy production [6]. According to RES integration, it can be supplementary, supporting the main power system, or stand-alone, completely satisfying the energy demand. A third option includes the possibility of generating an exceeded amount of energy, but it is feasible only for small and simple DC [6]. However, usually RES can rarely supply all the energy demand, so the integration is the most adopted solution [8]. Besides the PUE, other parameters such as the Green Energy Coefficient (GEC), the Energy Reuse Factor (ERF), and the Carbon Usage Effectiveness (CUE) should be considered in the renewable energy adoption [6].

Recently, DTs have emerged as transformative technology in this context. A DT is a digital replica of a physical system that continuously collects real-time data to simulate, monitor, and optimize the system's performance with a bidirectional link between the physical world and the virtual model. So, a DT for DC (DT4DC) should provide a virtual replica of the physical environment in both structure and behaviour, enabling predictive activities, supporting the decision-making process for DC optimization. DT potential lies in representing a complex system as the DC in a virtual environment. [2,3], enabling scenario-based simulations and real-time monitoring. DCs components usually feature communication interfaces providing real time data exchange [3] enabling the connection to the physical DC in a bidirectional information exchange [1]. For HPC centers, DTs offer a promising solution to address sustainability challenges. They enable real-time monitoring of resource usage, predictive analytics for energy management, and seamless integration of renewable energy sources, thereby enhancing efficiency and reducing emissions. Moreover, thanks to the dynamics of technology, the DT can be exploited for energy consumption simulation aimed at introducing saving strategies [5], supported by IoT and sensing devices, useful for DC's monitoring and management [3].

The paper explores the potential of DTs in sustainable HPC (S-HPC) practices, focusing on the University of Turin's S-HPC4AI project, which aims to develop a low-impact HPC center by leveraging RES and advanced cooling systems. By integrating DTs with advanced energy solutions, the S-HPC4AI initiative can set a benchmark for future energy-efficient, low-carbon HPC infrastructures [29]. In addition, the paper presents an ongoing operational experience on the HPC4AI DC as a first implementation that is coherent with the methodology and reference architecture formalized in this work. In HPC4AI, BIM-based representations are aligned with IoT time-series through stable identifiers and repeatable mapping mechanisms, enabling BIM-linked monitoring and alerting and providing preliminary empirical evidence on the implementability of the proposed approach [28].

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

This work is motivated by the lack of consensus on architectural principles for DTs in buildings and DCs. Although research on DTs has expanded, most studies target specific applications, such as thermal modeling, energy optimization, or fault detection, without addressing the overall system architecture that connects these elements [8][9]. Consequently, current solutions remain fragmented and difficult to generalize. Existing reviews emphasize that consistent data acquisition and semantic integration between BIM and IoT systems are essential foundations for any advanced DT capability [4][7]. However, BIM models and sensor data are often managed separately, limiting the ability to perform integrated analyses or implement control strategies.

For DC operators, this fragmentation leads to duplicated effort, inconsistent datasets, and limited operational insight. To address these issues, the paper proposes a reference architecture for DTs in DCs, structured around a layered framework that integrates BIM-based semantic models, real-time data, and analytical tools. The architecture aims to provide a coherent, technology-agnostic foundation for DT deployment, bridging the gap between conceptual models and practical implementation. Ultimately, it supports ongoing efforts toward standardized, interoperable DT frameworks applicable across the built environment.

A. Digital Twins in the Built Environment

The concept of the Digital Twin has been progressively adopted in the built environment to cope with the increasing complexity of buildings and infrastructure systems. While early definitions of Digital Twins emerged in manufacturing and aerospace domains, recent adaptations emphasize lifecycle integration, real-time data synchronization, and decision support for operational management [10]. In the context of buildings, Digital Twins are commonly described as digital representations that combine geometric models, system descriptions, and live operational data to support monitoring, analysis, and control.

A substantial body of literature has explored the application of Digital Twins to smart buildings, with proposed use cases ranging from energy efficiency optimization to predictive maintenance and occupant comfort management [3][11]. These studies often highlight the potential of Digital Twins to provide a holistic view of building performance, integrating information that is traditionally scattered across design documents, sensor platforms, and management systems.

However, several authors note that the term "Digital Twin" is frequently used inconsistently in the building domain. In many cases, solutions labeled as DTs correspond to static BIM models enhanced with sensor dashboards, or to simulation models that are periodically updated but not continuously synchronized with the physical system [5][12]. This conceptual ambiguity complicates the evaluation of proposed approaches and obscures the architectural requirements necessary to support genuine DT functionality.

Recent review papers attempt to clarify this landscape by identifying common characteristics and maturity levels of building DTs. These works consistently emphasize the importance of continuous data integration, semantic coherence, and bidirectional interaction between digital and physical systems [4][7]. From this perspective, the

architectural design of a Digital Twin system becomes a central concern, as it determines how data, models, and control mechanisms are coordinated.

B. Digital Twins for DCs

Compared to other building typologies, DCs have received relatively limited attention in DT literature. Nevertheless, the characteristics of DCs make them particularly suitable candidates for DT applications. The presence of dense sensing infrastructures, well-defined operational objectives, and strong coupling between physical and digital processes aligns well with the core principles of the DT paradigm.

Existing studies on DC DTs typically focus on specific subsystems or performance aspects. Several works investigate the use of simulation models to analyze airflow distribution and thermal behavior within data halls [13][14]. These studies demonstrate that detailed digital models can support improved cooling strategies and hotspot detection. Other contributions explore energy efficiency optimization, often combining sensor data with analytical or machine learning models to predict power usage effectiveness or cooling demand [15][16].

While these approaches provide valuable insights, they are often developed as standalone solutions, tightly coupled with specific data sources or modeling tools. As a result, they offer limited guidance on how different components should be integrated into a coherent DT system. In particular, the relationship between design data, operational measurements, and control systems is frequently left implicit or addressed through ad-hoc integrations.

Moreover, many DC DT implementations rely on simplified representations of building geometry and systems, neglecting the rich information available in BIM models. This simplification may be sufficient for certain analyses but limits the ability to reason about spatial relationships, asset hierarchies, and system interdependencies at scale. As DCs evolve and undergo frequent reconfigurations, maintaining accurate and up-to-date digital representations becomes increasingly challenging.

C. Role of BIM and IFC in Digital Twins

Building Information Modeling has become a central element of digitalization efforts in the construction and operation of buildings. BIM models provide detailed descriptions of building geometry, materials, systems, and components, typically structured according to standardized schemas such as Industry Foundation Classes. IFC enables vendor-neutral exchange of BIM data and supports interoperability across different software tools [6][17].

In the context of Digital Twins, BIM is often regarded as a foundational layer that provides spatial and semantic context. Several authors argue that BIM models can serve as a “digital backbone” for integrating operational data, enabling a consistent representation of assets throughout the building lifecycle [18]. This perspective is particularly relevant for DCs, where understanding the spatial arrangement of racks, cooling units, and airflow paths is essential for performance analysis.

Despite this potential, the integration of BIM and Digital Twins remains problematic. IFC schemas are complex and were primarily designed to support design and construction workflows, rather than real-time operational monitoring. Consequently, extracting and managing BIM data for Digital

Twin applications often requires significant preprocessing and customization [19].

Furthermore, BIM models are typically created at a specific point in time and may not reflect subsequent changes in the physical system unless actively maintained. In DCs, where equipment is frequently added, removed, or relocated, this lack of synchronization can quickly undermine the usefulness of BIM-based representations. Several studies highlight the need for mechanisms to keep BIM models aligned with operational realities, either through automated updates or through integration with asset management systems [20].

D. IoT Data Acquisition and Time-Series Management

IoT technologies play a central role in enabling DTs by providing continuous streams of operational data. In DCs, IoT infrastructures encompass a wide range of sensors measuring environmental conditions, energy consumption, and equipment status. These sensors generate high-frequency time-series data that must be reliably collected, stored, and processed.

The management of time-series data is a well-established research and industrial domain, with numerous platforms and databases optimized for high-throughput ingestion and query performance [21]. In building and DC applications, time-series data supports a variety of functions, including anomaly detection, trend analysis, and predictive modeling.

However, while IoT platforms are effective at handling large volumes of data, they often lack mechanisms for semantic integration. Sensor identifiers and data streams are typically managed independently of building models or asset descriptions, making it difficult to relate measurements to specific physical entities. This limitation is widely recognized in literature as a barrier to advanced analytics and DT development [7][22].

Several approaches have been proposed to address this issue, including the use of ontologies, semantic web technologies, and asset registries to link sensor data with building elements [23][24]. These approaches aim to provide a shared vocabulary and structure for representing assets and their associated data, facilitating interoperability across systems. Nevertheless, their adoption in DC contexts remains limited, and there is a lack of consensus on best practices.

E. Interoperability and Architectural Challenges

Interoperability emerges as a recurring theme across studies on DTs for buildings and infrastructure. The integration of BIM, IoT, analytics, and control systems involves multiple standards, data formats, and communication protocols, each developed for different purposes. Without a coherent architectural framework, DT implementations risk becoming brittle and difficult to maintain.

Several authors argue that architectural considerations should be treated as first-class concerns in DT research, rather than as implementation details [9][25]. From this perspective, a reference architecture can provide a shared understanding of system components, their responsibilities, and their interactions. Such architectures are common in other domains, such as enterprise systems and industrial automation, but are less mature in the building sector.

In the context of DCs, architectural challenges are compounded by operational constraints and legacy systems.

Building Management Systems and DC infrastructure management platforms often operate as closed systems, exposing limited interfaces for integration. This fragmentation restricts the ability to implement closed-loop control strategies that leverage advanced analytics or simulation models.

The literature reviewed in this section highlights a clear gap between the conceptual promise of DTs and their practical realization in DCs. While individual technologies such as BIM, IoT, and analytics are well established, their integration into a coherent and interoperable DT system remains an open challenge. Addressing this gap requires an architectural approach that explicitly accounts for data, semantics, models, and control, providing a structured foundation for future developments.

III. INTEROPERABILITY BOTTLENECKS AND SEMANTIC

A. Integration Challenges

A recurring theme in the literature on DTs for buildings and DCs is the fragmentation of digital representations across different lifecycle stages and technological domains. Design information, operational data, analytical models, and control logic are typically managed by distinct systems, each optimized for a specific purpose. While this specialization enables efficiency within individual domains, it creates significant barriers to integration when a holistic DT approach is pursued.

In the building sector, Building Information Modeling has become the dominant paradigm for representing design intent and physical configuration. BIM models encapsulate geometric, topological, and functional information about building components, often with a high level of detail. However, these models are usually produced during the design and construction phases and are not systematically updated during operation [26]. As a result, the digital representation maintained in BIM tools may diverge from the actual state of the building over time.

Conversely, operational systems such as IoT platforms and Building Management Systems focus on real-time data acquisition and control but typically lack an explicit representation of building structure or asset relationships. Sensor data streams are often identified by opaque identifiers that carry little semantic meaning beyond their immediate context. This disconnect makes it difficult to aggregate, analyze, and interpret data in relation to the physical system, especially in complex environments such as DCs.

The absence of a unified representation across these domains undermines the core premise of DTs, which relies on continuous synchronization between the physical and digital counterparts. Without architectural mechanisms to reconcile static and dynamic representations, DT implementations risk becoming collections of loosely connected tools rather than integrated systems.

B. BIM-IoT Integration as a Critical Bottleneck

Among the various integration challenges identified in the literature, the alignment of BIM data with IoT-generated time-series data is consistently highlighted as a critical bottleneck [4][7][22]. BIM models provide a rich semantic description of building elements, including their spatial relationships and functional roles. IoT data, on the other hand, provides granular, time-dependent measurements that reflect the actual behavior of the system.

Bridging these two domains is non-trivial. BIM elements and IoT sensors are typically created and managed independently, often by different stakeholders and using different tools. There is rarely a standardized mechanism to associate a sensor with the specific building element or system it monitors. In DCs, where thousands of sensors may be deployed across racks, cooling units, and power distribution components, this problem becomes particularly pronounced. Several studies report that BIM-IoT integration is frequently achieved through manual mapping or project-specific conventions [27]. While such approaches may be sufficient for pilot projects or small-scale deployments, they do not scale well and are prone to errors. Manual mappings are difficult to maintain over time, especially in environments where assets are frequently reconfigured, as is common in DCs.

Moreover, BIM schemas such as IFC were not originally designed to accommodate high-frequency time-series data. Although extensions and external linkages are possible, they require careful architectural design to avoid overloading BIM models with operational data or duplicating information across systems [19]. This tension between static and dynamic representations lies at the heart of many integration challenges.

C. Semantic Consistency and Asset Identification

Semantic consistency is a fundamental requirement for effective DT systems. It refers to the ability to consistently identify and reason about physical assets, spaces, and systems across different digital representations. In the absence of semantic consistency, analytics and control logic may operate on incomplete or ambiguous information, leading to suboptimal or even erroneous decisions.

In DC environments, semantic consistency is particularly challenging due to the diversity of assets and the hierarchical structure of systems. A single data hall may contain hundreds of racks, each hosting multiple servers, connected to cooling and power infrastructures that span multiple spatial and functional levels. Representing these relationships in a coherent and machine-readable form is essential for meaningful analysis.

The literature proposes various approaches to address semantic integration challenges, including the use of ontologies, linked data, and semantic middleware [23][28]. These approaches aim to provide a shared conceptual model that can be used to align BIM entities, sensor data, and analytical models. While promising, their adoption in operational settings remains limited, often due to perceived complexity or lack of tool support.

An alternative approach discussed in recent studies involves the use of asset registries as intermediary components [29]. An asset registry maintains a catalog of physical assets, their identifiers, and their relationships to sensors, models, and control points. By decoupling asset identification from specific data sources, such registries can provide a stable reference layer that supports integration across systems. This concept plays a central role in the architecture proposed in this paper.

D. Time-Series Data and Contextualization

Time-series data is a defining characteristic of operational DTs. In DCs, time-series measurements provide insights into

environmental conditions, energy consumption, and system performance. However, raw time-series data has limited value in isolation. Its usefulness depends on the ability to contextualize measurements within the physical and operational structure of the facility.

Contextualization involves associating time-series data with spatial locations, asset types, and operational states. For example, a temperature reading becomes more meaningful when it is linked to a specific rack, aisle, or cooling zone. Without such context, analytics may fail to capture localized phenomena such as hotspots or airflow imbalances.

Several authors note that contextualization is often treated as an afterthought in DT implementations [22][30]. Sensor data is collected and stored efficiently, but the semantic relationships needed to interpret it are either implicit or encoded in application-specific logic. This approach limits reusability and complicates the integration of new analytics or visualization tools.

From an architectural perspective, contextualization should be addressed explicitly, rather than being embedded in individual applications. This requires a dedicated layer or mechanism that associates time-series data with semantic representations derived from BIM or asset models. Such an approach aligns with the layered architecture proposed in this paper and addresses a key gap identified in the literature.

E. Integration of Analytics and Control

Beyond data integration, DTs are expected to support advanced analytics and, ultimately, interaction with control systems. Analytics may include physics-based simulations, data-driven models, or hybrid approaches that combine both. In DCs, these analytics are often used to predict thermal behavior, estimate energy consumption, or identify anomalies.

The integration of analytics into a DT architecture raises additional challenges. Analytical models require well-defined inputs and assumptions, which must be aligned with the data and semantics of the DT. Inconsistent or poorly structured data can significantly degrade model performance and reliability [31].

Furthermore, closing the loop between analytics and control requires careful consideration of system boundaries and responsibilities. Control actions in DCs, such as adjusting cooling setpoints or airflow rates, are typically managed by Building Management Systems or specialized control platforms. Integrating these systems with a DT raises questions of safety, reliability, and governance.

The literature highlights that many DT implementations stop short of closed-loop control, focusing instead on decision support for human operators [12][25]. While this approach reduces risk, it also limits the potential benefits of DT. Achieving higher levels of automation requires architectures that clearly defines how analytical insights are translated into control actions and how feedback from the physical system is incorporated.

So, the analysis presented in this section underscores several gaps in the current state of DT research and practice for DCs. First, there is a lack of architectural frameworks that systematically address the integration of BIM, IoT data, analytics, and control. Second, semantic consistency and asset identification remain persistent challenges, particularly in complex and dynamic environments. Third, the

contextualization of time-series data is often insufficiently addressed, limiting the effectiveness of analytics and decision support. These gaps motivate the need for a reference architecture that explicitly structures the DT system into well-defined layers, each with clear responsibilities and interfaces. *Such* architecture should support interoperability, scalability, and reuse, while accommodating the specific requirements of DC operation. The following section introduces the proposed reference architecture and outlines its main design principles.

IV. REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE FOR DC DIGITAL TWINS

The analysis of existing literature highlights that the main limitations of current DT implementations for buildings and DCs are not related to the availability of sensing technologies or analytical methods, but rather to the absence of coherent and reusable architectural frameworks. Several recent reviews emphasize that fragmentation between design data, operational measurements, analytics, and control systems represents a major obstacle to the deployment of effective DTs in the built environment [4][7]. In response to this gap, this section introduces a reference architecture for DTs applied to DCs, explicitly designed to integrate BIM-based representations, IoT data acquisition, analytical models, and control mechanisms within a unified and interoperable system.

The proposed architecture is grounded in the principle of separation of concerns. Rather than merging all functionalities into a monolithic platform, the DT is structured into a limited number of coordinated layers, each responsible for a specific aspect of system representation or operation. This layered approach is consistent with best practices in software and systems engineering and reflects recommendations emerging from recent DT studies, which stress the importance of modularity and interoperability for scalability and long-term maintainability [4][7]. The architecture promotes interoperability by design, acknowledging that DCs typically rely on heterogeneous platforms for design, monitoring, and control, often provided by different vendors and evolving over time.

A central design principle of the architecture is semantic alignment between static and dynamic information. Static BIM data and dynamic IoT measurements are not directly coupled but are aligned through shared semantic references, ensuring that analytical models and control logic operate on consistent representations of physical assets and systems. At the same time, the architecture supports incremental adoption. While advanced DTs may ultimately enable automated control strategies, the proposed framework allows DT functionality to be initially deployed for monitoring and decision support, while preserving the possibility of progressively tighter integration with control systems as operational confidence increases.

The reference architecture is structured into five logical layers, each contributing to the overall DT functionality (Figure 1). The data layer is responsible for ingesting and storing heterogeneous data sources, including BIM models encoded in IFC, IoT sensor measurements, and external contextual information. Data is handled in its native form, using storage technologies appropriate to its characteristics, such as object

repositories for BIM files and time-series databases for sensor data.

Fig. 1. High-level overview of the layered reference architecture for a DCDT.

Above this, the semantic layer (Figure 2) provides the mechanisms required to contextualize and align data across sources. A key element of this layer is an asset registry that maintains consistent identifiers and relationships for physical assets, spaces, sensors, analytical models, and control points. By acting as an intermediary between BIM models and IoT platforms, the semantic layer avoids embedding operational data directly into BIM representations, thereby improving maintainability and scalability.

Fig. 2. Conceptual role of the semantic layer, aligning BIM-based representations and IoT data within the DT architecture.

Building on this foundation, the model layer hosts the digital representations that constitute the core of the DT, including geometric and topological models derived from BIM, as well as physical or data-driven models describing thermal behavior, airflow, or energy consumption. These models consume semantically enriched data and expose standardized interfaces for higher-level processing. The analytics layer builds on the model layer to provide functionality such as performance assessment, anomaly detection, forecasting, and optimization, operating at different levels of abstraction from individual components to entire data halls. Finally, the actuation layer represents the interface between the DT and the physical DC, translating analytical outcomes into operational actions through interaction with existing management and control systems, while supporting different levels of automation appropriate to the critical nature of DC operations.

Thus, actuation is conceived as a governed interface: actions derived from analytics (e.g., cooling setpoint changes or airflow adjustments) are filtered through safety envelopes (temperature/humidity/dew-point constraints), rate limiting,

role-based authorization, and audit logging, with explicit rollback policies and manual override. This design supports progressive automation from advisory recommendations to supervised control, while preserving fail-safe fallback to baseline BMS/DCIM rules in case of sensor faults or degraded data quality.

While the reference architecture remains technology-agnostic, it is compatible with widely adopted standards and interfaces typically used in DCs, including IFC4/IFC4.3 for BIM exchange, REST/HTTP or MQTT for IoT data access, and BMS/DCIM integration through common building and industrial protocols (e.g., BACnet/IP, Modbus, OPC-UA), while semantic tagging approaches (e.g., Brick/Haystack/NGSI-LD) can be adopted where a formal knowledge layer is required.

V. PILOT INSTANTIATION AND PRELIMINARY INTEGRATION METRICS

A pilot example of instantiation of the architecture is provided by the University of Turin HPC4AI DC. It provides an operational setting where BIM-based representations and IoT time-series are aligned through stable identifiers and repeatable mapping mechanisms, enabling BIM-linked monitoring and alerting workflows [28]. Operational measurements are collected through the facility monitoring stack and stored in a time-series repository, and a BIM model derived from as-built documentation acts as the semantic and spatial reference. Sensor-to-asset associations are maintained through stable identifiers (e.g., rack- and zone-level IDs) and mapping rules implemented through BIM shared parameters and synchronization scripts, enabling consistent contextualization of time-series values within the building representation. This pilot is not intended as a full quantitative benchmarking of energy savings, but it provides preliminary evidence that the proposed semantic alignment and synchronization approach is implementable in a real DC environment with measurable integration overhead. Table I reports preliminary integration metrics that quantify refresh configuration, end-to-end responsiveness, and mapping effort. Beyond the single pilot, these indicators are proposed as a minimal, reusable set to assess architecture compliance and operational readiness across DT4DC deployments: they include (i) context descriptors (facility scale and operational data backbone), (ii) compliance checks (BIM role and mapping strategy), and (iii) readiness metrics (observability through synchronized variables, configured refresh interval, and end-to-end update latency). In addition, Table I includes a replicability indicator, namely mapping effort per onboarded sensor stream, and an example of actionable output enabled by semantic alignment. The same architecture will be exploited for stronger validation within S-HPC4AI, where sustainability-oriented KPIs and broader operational constraints represent the next step [29].

TABLE I. PRELIMINARY INTEGRATION METRICS

Metric	HPC4AI report/measure	Importance	Status (C/P/N/NA) ^a
Facility scale	16 racks (context size)	Sets domain complexity and comparability	C

<i>Metric</i>	<i>HPC4AI report/measure</i>	<i>Importance</i>	<i>Status (C/P/N/NA)^a</i>
Operational data backbone	Time-series repository used as operational data source	Shows that data comes from real operational monitoring, verifying that there's an operational and auditable database	C
BIM role	As-built BIM semantic/spatial reference	Clarifies the role of BIM as semantic/spatial backbone	C
Mapping strategy	Stable IDs and BIM shared parameters for sensor/asset association	Measures the quality of the semantic alignment and quantifies how it is realized in practice	C
Variables synchronized	Temperature, humidity, dew point, timestamp/status flags	Demonstrates which signals support analytics/alerts and if the DT has sufficient observability for the objectives.	C
Refresh interval, Δt (configured parameter)	Synchronization period (e.g., every 60 s / 5 min)	Defines DT operating mode, classifying its class: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • near-real-time (sec-min) for operation • quasi real-time (min) for supervision • batch (hours) for reporting 	P
End-to-end update latency, $t_{DT} - t_{DB}$	Time (in seconds) Delay between DB availability and DT update (report median; optionally 95 th percentile)	Measures responsiveness from sensing to DT view, to know if the architecture is implemented consistently with the use case	P
Mapping effort	Minutes to onboard one sensor stream: assign SensorID, bind to asset, register stream metadata, verify first update (report median; optionally Interquartile Range (IQR))	Estimates onboarding cost per additional sensor and verify the real dynamics of the twin, it measures the scalability and replicability	P
Output example	Concrete pilot output enabled by alignment (e.g., hotspot/threshold alert localized on rack/zone; optional: alerts/week)	Shows actionable outcome with value realisation checkpoint	C

^a. Status legend: C = Compliant/available (implemented and reported); P = Partial (implemented but only preliminarily measured or reported); N = Not implemented; NA = Not Applicable)

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a reference architecture for Digital Twins applied to DCs, motivated by the recurring limitations identified in current research and practice. A critical analysis of the literature highlighted that, despite the maturity of BIM, IoT, and analytical techniques, their integration within coherent DT systems remains weak. In particular, the lack of semantic alignment between static building representations

and dynamic operational data has been consistently reported as a major bottleneck for building-scale DT adoption.

The proposed architecture addresses this issue by introducing a layered organization that clearly separates data acquisition, semantic alignment, modeling, analytics, and interaction with control systems. By treating BIM-based representations as a semantic backbone rather than as repositories of operational data, the architecture avoids overloading design models while still exploiting their descriptive power. The introduction of an explicit semantic layer, centered on an asset registry, enables consistent identification and contextualization of IoT data, supporting scalable DT development in complex and evolving DC environments.

From an operational perspective, the architecture supports incremental adoption. DT functionality can initially focus on monitoring and decision support, leveraging contextualized data and analytical models, while preserving the possibility of tighter integration with control systems as confidence and organizational maturity increase. This aspect is particularly relevant for DCs, where reliability and risk management often limit the adoption of fully automated control strategies. A preliminary empirical evidence on implementability and basic integration metrics such as mapping effort and refresh latency, is given by the lightweight pilot instantiation based on the operational HPC4AI DC.

Several limitations of the proposed work should be acknowledged. First, the architecture is presented at a conceptual level and does not prescribe specific standards, protocols, or platforms. While this technology-agnostic approach enhances generality, it also implies that concrete implementation choices remain context-dependent. To reduce ambiguity on practical adoption, the paper also outlines compatible standards and interfaces commonly used in DCs (e.g., IFC for BIM exchange, REST/MQTT for IoT access, and BACnet/IP or Modbus for BMS/DCIM integration), while leaving concrete selections to deployment constraints. Second, the effectiveness of the semantic layer relies on the quality and maintenance of asset mappings, which may require organizational effort and governance processes not addressed in this paper.

Future developments will focus on validating the proposed architecture through real-world case studies in operational DCs. This includes assessing the effort required to establish and maintain the semantic layer, evaluating the impact of contextualized data on analytical accuracy, and exploring controlled forms of DT-driven actuation. In this perspective, S-HPC4AI represents the next iteration for extending the same architectural principles toward sustainability-driven objectives, broader sensing scopes, and more robust operational constraints.

Additional research is also needed to investigate standardization opportunities and to quantify the benefits of DT adoption in terms of energy efficiency, operational resilience, and lifecycle management.

In conclusion, this work contributes an architectural foundation for DTs in DCs that directly addresses known integration challenges. By focusing on interoperability, semantic consistency, and architectural clarity, the proposed reference architecture provides a practical and reusable basis for advancing DT research and deployment in this critical domain.

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